

Anamorphosis

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Abstract. *Anamorphosis is about the processing of two contrasting structures exposed in the first part of the composition. One has more gestural character, the other is more textured. Both structures are based on a short sound of a wooden door, which, however, does not appear in its original form in the composition. The structural nature of this basic material, especially the fast repetitions changing in time, leads to spectral and temporal variants of these structures, developed in the second and third - more reprise-like - part of the composition. Anamorphosis has been invited for performance at the World New Music Days 2019 in Tallinn, Estonia and has been awarded at "XIII° International Destellos Competition 2020" (Argentina) and "21th Weimarer Frühjahrstage für zeitgenössische Musik" (Germany) - 1st price and audience award.*

Spatialisation: *Ambisonic*

Duration: *7:19*

Year: *2017*

Keywords: *acousmatic music; surround sound; ambisonic; immersive*